

Memory and Neurolinguistic Function in the Deaf

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Abstract. The Deaf community's relationship with language provides a new angle from which to study the role of phonemic elements in the interaction between lexemes and memory. Departing from a hearing canon and exploring a broader spectrum of language perception and production, we are able to revise questions on and develop insight into cognitive processes that influence memory. This paper will not attempt to ascertain whether the Deaf or the hearing have better memories; neurocognitive discrepancies between the groups prevent certain abilities from being compared under the same criteria. But there is no comprehensive "better," only the space afforded by these discrepancies that allows for deeper understanding of neurolinguistic processes in conjunction with memory. To investigate the processes that influence Deaf memory, I compare studies on American Sign Language (ASL) and Japanese Sign Language (JSL). This comparison finds that when research on memory in the Deaf compared to the hearing is limited to English, the Deaf's supposed deficit is the fault of the English language rather than a lack of phonological information. Linguistic models allow for a detailed understanding of information retrieval and the role of memory within language production. They also can narrow down variables of language-specific stimulus and when and where in cognition they come into play. The current standardized models of language production do not account for an inability to perceive audition. Thus, this paper will conclude by proposing a new Deaf language production model.

Keywords: Deaf linguistics; ASL; neurolinguistics; sociolinguistics; language production; memory

1 Introduction

The role of memory in psycholinguistics is indisputable. It has been seen as the groundwork on which all fundamental linguistic processes are built; lexical entry, access, and retrieval all combine memory with neurological interaction. In coordination with memory, physical senses of sight and hearing grant orthography and phonology. Research has determined phonology one of the most important factors in the recognition of cognates and the creation of links between lexical and semantic items. But when the phonological component is absent, how does this impact memory, our essential hard drive? The Deaf community's relationship with language provides a new angle at which to study the facilitating role of phonological elements in the interaction between lexemes and memory. It is necessary to look outside the canon of hearing memory processes and instead consider how this restrictive standard affects an understanding of Deaf brains and memory, as well as its impact on the education of Deaf children. As research in Deaf memory and language production continues to emerge, revised questions on cognitive processes and neurological structures follow. Retracing the processes behind Deaf language production allows for a step-by-step understanding of Deaf memory function and its interaction with language use. Thus, to conclude this paper, a Deaf language production model will be proposed, considering both neurological and socialized contributions to memory in the Deaf.

2 Neurolinguistic processes behind memory

2.1 Functionality of memory in the Deaf and the hearing

Almost every linguistic process involves phonology. Increasing research on phonology in language acquisition and production reveals just how crucial sound is. The 1999 Dijkstra et al. article, 'Recognition of cognates and interlingual homographs: The neglected role of phonology,' tested lexical access processes of bilinguals. The article studied how phonological similarities between the stimulus and a non-target word affected or influenced stimulus performance. Dijkstra (1999) noted that phonological factors are often overlooked regarding recognition, despite phonology playing a mediating role when the orthography of words is different. Phonological similarity between interlingual words proved an inhibitory contribution to reaction time for bilinguals; when there was a phonological overlap, the reaction time was slower. Monolinguals, on the other hand, with only one lexicon to sort through, were able to recognise non-words faster and with more accuracy.

Despite the abundance of literature on phonological importance, research on the effects of the absence of sound is an almost untapped domain. Comprehensive linguistic concepts must be reconsidered when phonology becomes inapplicable. Some linguistic facets, such as those tested by Dijkstra (1999), are hindered by an inability to perceive audition. Even the most rudimentary are impacted, down to the first stages of speech perception. For example, how would the accepted Cohort model account for a lack of acoustic stimulus? Activation, the first step of Cohort, is influenced by solely acoustic properties. The next step, selection, sorts through the activated cohort, or group of phonetically similar words. But the Deaf would not perceive phonetically similar words; without phonemes, the inhibitory factors of homophones and false friends are eliminated. Form still plays a role in a Deaf person's language activation and retrieval, but manifests differently than that of a hearing person's. Orthography and signs represent form for the Deaf, the latter replacing a hearing person's phonology. The presence of both orthography and signs, known as Simultaneous Communication or SimCom, is likened to bilingualism because the Deaf also possess two combined, simultaneously activated lexicons. SimCom's dual encoding accounts for slower orthographic word recognition and processing speed in the Deaf. Additionally, both Deaf and hearing people experience a form of memory load, the amount of information the brain can perceive and remember at a single moment. When there's an overload, hesitation phenomena occurs: as 'memory load increases, performance decreases' (Dehn, 2011, p. 61). This can present in hearing people as tongue twisters, the same phenomenon called finger fumblers in the Deaf. Repeats and false starts are universal quirks of language, extending to slips of the hand for the Deaf, especially with formationally or locationally similar signs. However, the difference in how the brain processes information comes into play as the memory load increases. As a Deaf person's memory becomes more saturated, their language performance will begin to deteriorate sooner than a hearing person's would (Dehn, 2011, p. 65). Seemingly, it is the process of sequential recall that is formulated and conceptualized differently in hearing and Deaf brains.

An individual's memory capacity is directly linked to language comprehension and acquisition (Hamilton, 2011). Because critical aspects of language acquisition, such as attention and processing speed, can suffer from a lack of auditory perception, it is in these processes that the hearing seemingly perform better than the Deaf. When a Deaf child is unable to develop sequential processing skills early enough and apply them to the brain's processing of linguistic information, their understanding of syntax may suffer (Hamilton, 2011). The ability to confidently grasp syntactic order is crucial in language development. If a

Deaf child does not completely master this, they may suffer impediments in learning and comprehending either signed or printed linguistic information. Language delay is common in Deaf children as a result, with only '50% of Deaf high school students reading at the fourth-grade level or below upon graduation' (Hamilton, 2011, p. 408). This suggests early intervention for strengthening syntactic order can be critical. However, this deficit cannot solely be attributed to a Deaf person's brain processes. Lack of 'accessible linguistic interaction with other signers and less than sufficient working memory skills to assist Deaf children during language learning period' are external factors that impact the memory capabilities of the Deaf (Hamilton, 2011, p. 408). Factors of linguistic inequality and a desire for Deaf children to speak or lip read instead of sign also comes into play. Despite being tested on the same technical skills, neurocognitive discrepancies between the Deaf and hearing prevents those skills from being compared using the same criteria. Perhaps this supposed deficit appears not because the Deaf are deficient to the hearing, but because the hearing standard forced upon them attempts to stimulate a neural pathway that simply does not exist.

2.2 Linguistic strengths of Deaf memory

In other areas, however, a lack of auditory perception boosts memory. In both nonlinguistic and linguistic terms, the Deaf have performed better than the hearing in tasks where information is presented in 'static visuospatial format' (Hamilton, 2011, p. 407). Visuospatial memory is involved in 'recalling and manipulating images to remain oriented in space and keep track of the location of moving objects' (Dehn, 2011, p. 80). Examples of impairment in visuospatial processing include difficulty driving due to an incorrect judgement of distance or other objects in the environment. The boost in this type of memory of Deaf individuals could also be seen as a form of linguistic determinism; biologically, the Deaf brain has adapted for improved visuospatial memory to make up for a lack of acoustic memory and perception. A hearing person's auditory cortex helps them process and comprehend sound, but in a Deaf person's brain, it becomes part of working memory (Cardin, 2018). Instead of being allocated to auditory processing, the cortex is now involved in cognitive processing, which accounts for a Deaf person's heightened memory and comprehension of locative and visual movement.

Compared to the hearing, Deaf brains perform better on visuospatial linguistic tasks such as arrays of 'blocks on a table or objects in a grid' (Hamilton, 2011, p. 406). This was determined by the Corsi block-tapping test and the Knox cube test. In the former, the experimenter 'touched blocks randomly arranged on a board' in a sequence, which would then be replicated by the subject (Hamilton, 2011, p. 406). In the latter, the same sequential task was created, but instead of a random arrangement, the blocks were in a straight line. In both experiments, Deaf participants proved superior to hearing participants in recalling these visual patterns and successive figures. Just as some cognitive functions in the hearing allow them to perform better on certain tasks, other functions in Deaf brains grant capabilities the hearing lack. Because of the physicality of sign language and the sequential memory involved in structuring and understanding the syntax and grammar of rapid hand movements, it is more than reasonable that the Deaf would perform better on these tasks.

3 The role of the English language

The previous comparisons of linguistic and nonlinguistic memory have been between hearing English speakers and American Sign Language users. But as with the brain's adaptation to a lack of audition,

memory function can be somewhat attributed to linguistic determinism and dependent upon the language itself. To investigate the influence of language-specific stimulus, I will compare memory function in American Sign Language (ASL) and Japanese Sign Language (JSL). JSL users were found to have better short and long term memories than ASL users, but so were Japanese speakers compared to English speakers (Flaherty, 2000, p. 243). A language's alphabet often has an innate connection between orthography and phonology, but since Deaf people have never encoded auditory features of language, so they're unable to recognise multiple phonemes. One consequence of this is that there is no positive correlation between phonemic awareness and reading comprehension. Many languages rely on this phonological encoding to build stronger cognitive links, but in languages like Japanese that is not the case (Hamilton, 2011). With three alphabets, kanji, hiragana, and katakana, the logogens build upon each other, rather than rely solely on phonological association. Kanji characters are meaning-based rather than sound-based like the English alphabet. In essence, this is sign language. Kanji's 'finite set of radicals and forms are spatially and visually related to one another in writing,' eliminating the necessity of sound to glean meaning. When reading, the Japanese Deaf use visual properties of letters, so they don't suffer from a lack of auditory perception when there's already no orthographic-phonetic correspondence. In Japanese, there are 2,000 kanji, almost 80 times English's 26 letters. Readers of Japanese, hearing or Deaf, simply must encode, and thus remember, more visual shapes and sequences than English readers. This innately circumvents poor sequential memory, so when compared to English speakers, Japanese speakers will prove more successful at memory tasks involving short-term sequential skills.

Perhaps when research on memory in the Deaf compared to the hearing is limited to ASL, the Deaf's deficit is the fault of the English language rather than a lack of phonological information. Is memory then a result of linguistic determinism? In the same way Russians take longer to categorize blue because of the way their language lexically orders colours, do the Japanese simply engage with the world in a different, more retentive way because of unconscious factors of their language? Flaherty and Aidan's 2004 study of sequential memory in Deaf and hearing students using English or Japanese addressed this, highlighting a key difference in how the students went about a short-term memory task (Flaherty & Aidan, 2004). Their research advanced the theory that the Japanese are influenced by technical aspects of their language, and so their mindsets are structured to remember sequences more adeptly. Two experiments were conducted. The participants were tested first on a series of words, then on abstract lines and shapes. In both experiments, the Japanese participants outperformed the English-signing or speaking. Flaherty (2000) notes that the study confirms 'the superior visuo-spatial memory of the Japanese' (Flaherty, 2000, p. 241). Students using JSL said they used 'a visual gestalt memory strategy, seeing the sequence as a whole,' whereas students using ASL said they saw the words as just a sequence (Hamilton, 2011, p. 406). This raises another question. Do the Deaf really have an elevated capacity for visual memory when verbal memory is eliminated? Or is 'a deficit in recall of English linguistic material more a function of the idiosyncrasies of written English rather than a deficit in recall of written material' (Flaherty & Aidan, 2004, p. 40)?

4 Constructing a new Deaf language production model

Research connecting Deaf memory deficits or surpluses to language production began to emerge in the 1970s. While many models of language production have been proposed, there is no one standardised form, much like the hearing bilingual model which continues to evolve as more research is realised. Deaf models by Fromkin (1971), Garrett (1975), Butterworth (1979), and the bilingual model by de Bot (2004) will serve

as groundwork for this paper’s culminating model. Bilingual language production is likely the most similar to Deaf language production, given the likeness of SimCom to bilingualism. Grosjean (2008) collates the stages of these models to outline a common one. Deaf language production begins with non-linguistic message formulation such as an idea or a thought. It’s then padded by pragmatic factors and grammatical structure assignment, and prosodic features are chosen. The next stage is termed ‘lexical look-up,’ which Grosjean defines as when ‘the signer enters her lexicon and chooses the appropriate lexical items’ (Grosjean, 1979, p. 324). Many factors involved in lexical activation are not wholly conscious, so an updated definition of lexical look-up would benefit Grosjean’s explanation. These items are then assembled and a command is sent to the motor control of the brain. If motor commands were replaced with overt speech, this model would look similar to Levelt’s. Levelt’s model notes that form comes before phonology in the formulating stage, meaning the application of audition and overt speech are the last steps of producing language. Among minor phonetic changes in the formulator, the articulating stage is the only phase that will be significantly altered when accounting for differing neurological function.

The proposed model combines the general structure of Levelt’s with the steps outlined by Grosjean (Grosjean, 1979). Elements of de Bot’s bilingual updates to Levelt’s model are also incorporated, including a combined lexicon. Figure 1 is a sketch of the model. Instead of the articulation and audition stages of Levelt’s, the proposed model has a motor control centre. Here, the content of the lexical plan is sent to the motor cortex, a Section of the brain’s frontal lobe in charge of the body’s movements, such as facial expressions and hand signs (‘The Motor Cortex’).

Figure 1: Redeveloped Deaf language production model.

Though de Bot's amendments to Levelt's model provide the groundwork for other models with dual encoding, not all of his suggestions would make sense in this application. Instead of having two separate languages with separate grammars and signifiers, as a bilingual would, a Deaf person's dual encoding is derived from the same base language, and thus it's unlikely there would be unequal command. De Bot adopted Green's (1986) idea of separate formulators for each language, but this is omitted in the Deaf model. De Bot's formulator generates meaning important to phonological processing and is largely language-specific, and in the Deaf model, phonology has been eliminated. A hearing person's perception of intonational meaning and metrical structure are different than a Deaf person's. Regarding the studies on ASL and JSL, is it possible to create a comprehensive Deaf model when there are such discrepancies in how language is processed and sorted language to language? In that respect, how vague must any model dealing with dual encoding be to account for linguistic determinism? The model proposed here is not exhaustive. It instead provides a simplified overview of Deaf language production based on reinterpretations of current models and the modern research aggregated for this paper.

5 Conclusion

The importance of studying Deaf memory and language production is an almost untapped resource in the field of psycholinguistics. The Deaf interact with language in a unique way. Their memories and perception of the world are influenced by a lack of audition, which no longer calls for an answer of better or worse but rather how and why. The hearing person's canon of language can be informed by the Deaf's; studying alternative memory function brings to light alternative learning strategies and competencies for all people. Many of the supposed deficiencies in Deaf memories can be remedied by engaging Deaf instructors to teach Deaf children, promoting communication through a Deaf lens rather than trying to conform to a hearing one. Creating a Deaf language production model helps to understand not only the many components that must align to facilitate language production but also the intricacies of the brain. But linguistic testing can only take us so far. It must be supplemented with brain scans and neurological tests for a view of the brain itself, not only how linguistic functions present verbally or nonverbally. Questions posed within this paper invite specialization on Deaf memory in fields such as neurolinguistics, linguistic anthropology, or sociolinguistics. Each study is a step closer to unravelling intricacies that will broaden perspectives on memory and neurolinguistic function. The realm of research on Deaf memory is ripe and ever-expanding, and its fruits are profoundly important to the Deaf community and linguistics as a whole.

6 References

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